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EMOTION AND PERCEPTION

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Upama Sarkar

*Phd Research Scholar,
 Department of Philosophy
 Presidency University,
 86/1 College Street,
 Kolkata- 700073*

ABSTRACT

The word 'emotion' and 'feeling' are just synonyms but we often used these words interchangeably. We have different types of emotions like happiness, sadness, anger, fear etc. The way we make decision, take action and perceive the reality are influenced by emotions. But can we say that we see emotions? Most of the answers will be negative. In this paper I would like to discuss about how emotion is related with perception. In virtual life we often use emoji or emoticons to express our emotion but is it sufficient to express emotions? We see the bodily expression and said that emotions have both private and public entities.

KEYWORDS: emotion, emoji, feeling, perception.

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* Corresponding Author

I. INTRODUCTION

Emotions are specific kind of subjective experiences and this idea has dominated emotion theory roughly from ancient Greece to the beginning of the twentieth century. Emotion is a complex experience of consciousness, bodily sensation and behavior that reflects the personal significance of thing, an event or a state of affairs. It is basically the class of feeling separated by their accomplished quality from other tangible encounters like tasting ice-cream or sensing a pain in someone's tooth. But feelings are experienced consciously and emotion is experienced both consciously and subconsciously. Emotions are related with bodily reaction that are actuated through synapses and chemicals delivered by the cerebrum. During the 1970, psychologist Paul Ekman identified six fundamental feelings that he recommended were all around experienced in every human culture. The emotions he recognized were happiness, sadness, disgust, fear, surprise and anger. He later expanded his list of basic emotions to include such things as pride, shame, embarrassment and excitement. There are various sorts of emotions that impact how we live and collaborate with others. Our emotions affect the decision we make, the moves we make and the perception we have. Emotion and perception are viewed as independent areas of study but the question is how does emotion affect perception? does emotion affect decision making? Without emotion we cannot make any decisions. And the another ques is can we see emotion? We can know our emotions but can we perceive another's emotional states? These issues are discussed in this paper.

The private and public emotion:

We know emotion is some kind of feelings and it is not completely covert and publicly perceivable. Emotions can be precisely seen in people. When I am happy, I might smile and jump for joy. When I am angry I may frown and gesture furtively. In this way bodily expressions express emotions but the bodily expression of emotion is different from the emotion itself. Most of the actor and actress can pretend a wide range of emotions simply by take their peer facial expression but they can do this without actually feeling the associated emotion. So we see that bodily expressions can be separated from emotions. Some phenomenologist argue that to see the bodily expression of emotion is to literally see the emotion itself and not merely an expression of the emotion. Max Scheler said that

"For we certainly believe ourselves to be directly acquainted with another person's joy in his laughter, with his sorrow and pain in his tears, with his shame in his blushing, with his entreaty in his outstretched hands, with his love in his look of affection, with his rage in his gnashing of his

teeth, with his threats in the clenching of his fist, and with the tenor of this thoughts in the sound of his words. If anyone tells me that this is not 'perception' [of the emotion itself], for it cannot be so, in view of the fact that a perception is simply a 'complex of physical sensations,' and that there is certainly no sensation of another person's mind nor any stimulus from such a source, I would beg him to turn aside from such questionable theories and address himself to the phenomenological facts."

Phenomenologist Scheler and Maurice Merleau-Ponty aid that our bodily behavior can express our emotion. Merleau-Ponty said that,

"I do not see anger or a threatening attitude as a psychic fact hidden behind the gesture, I read anger in it. The gesture does not make me think of anger, it is anger itself. I perceive the grief or anger of the other in his conduct, in the face or his hands, without recourse to any 'inner' experience of suffering or anger, and because grief and anger are variations of belonging to the world, undivided between the body and consciousness, and equally applicable to the other's conduct, visible in his phenomenal body, as in my own conduct as it is presented to me." we see the bodily expression so that is outer behavioral expression or public emotion and the consciousness or the mental state which we couldn't see is inner emotion or private emotion. Merleau-Ponty did not accept the difference between inner emotion and the expression of outer behavior. So if we see someone's angry gesture, we see the anger itself. Proper parts of emotion is constituted by the bodily expression of emotional phenomena. According to him perception is sufficient to know the another's mental state. Some philosophers deny this. According to Dretske and Goldie the real emotions are hidden, behavioral expressions are not the emotion itself.

Do emojis help us to express emotions:

now a days we are all busy on social media and most of the people use emoji when they post something or message someone. Emojis are handled by the mind as non-verbal data which implies that we decipher them as emotional communications. We use emojis in social media when we are feeling happy, sad, angry, surprised, sleepy and so on. The emojis we used most are face with tears of joy, red heart, rolling on the floor laughing, loudly crying face, smile face with heart eyes, thinking face, folded hands etc. to express our emotions. These days emojis conduct a key part of computer-mediated communication. Emoji permits individuals more really feelings and their characters, by expanding the semantic substance of visual messages. The Japanese word emoji means "picture word". When we are using natural language processing along with emoji we can extract semantics, express best signals, emotional status and personality layers among other characteristics from text. We can

find out the exact emoji to express our emotion and most of the time people by whom we communicate understand our emotion. Because when we send someone a smile or sad emoji that enhance a happier or sadder tone. Using of emoji is quick, regular and fun to stay attached with our family members, friends and loved one while working, travelling and living. In our modern communication we all are understanding the meaning of these emojis, for example, if we want to send someone "okay" we can explain this with particular emoji and in this case the person with whom we communicate, understand our message through this emoji. But in the case of expressing our feeling or emotion can we say that a emoji is sufficient to express our emotion? Emotion is subjective feeling and it is a kind of complex state of feeling. In virtual world we find ourselves very happy but may be we go through a lot of problems and didn't share them with anyone. For example, suppose I send someone happy emoji to express myself happy but at that time I have something else in my head. Most of the time we can understand other person's expression through the emoji and in our virtual life it has taken a place but social communication is better than virtual communication for exchanging our emotion with our friends and families.

Perceive the emotions:

We see the physical world by our eyes. Seeing , hearing, smelling, feeling, tastings are form of Sense perceptual knowledge but philosophers are focusing on visual perception. We can perceive emotions to see facial expression or bodily expression. It is not so easy to know the emotional state of other people. We can aware of our own emotion. Emotional self awareness is the capacity to precisely see your feelings, mark them and know that they start various sentiments that you can observe. Emotions are just personal experience and it is purely subjective in nature. We can directly perceive our inner mental state like emotion, hope, belief, desire but we don't have any direct knowledge of another mental state. When we are angry, we have direct access or direct feeling of our emotion. There are difference between perceive our own experience and perceiving others. Because we are different subject. The way I feel my emotion is different from someone who feel his emotion. When we are close to someone and in conversation we can understand they are happy or sad, though it is not to easy but we try to do this. We assume that other minds are exist. Mindreading is the ability to detect and respond the mental states like beliefs desires, emotions of other persons. 'theory-theory' and 'simulation theory' are two mechanism to solve the problem of others mind. We observe the behavior of others and we assume the mental states. There is another theory named 'direct-perception', according to this theory we have directly perceptual

access to aspects others mentality. Husserl writes that "we intuitively ascribe to the other person his lived experiencing, and we do this completely without mediation and without consciousness of any impressional or imaginative picturing". According to this theory we directly know others emotion, feelings and intention. Without inferential theories and simulation we perceive what other people are thinking and it is called smart perception. We immediately perceive the emotion, motives and feeling. By direct perception we understand others. We see bodily expression or action of other people so we see the meaning of these. According to co-present view when we see a tomato , we see a particular part of tomato which faces me but we nevertheless perceive the whole. Analogously we perceive the bodily behavior but nevertheless perceive mental phenomena like happiness or anger. The way we see the solid three-dimensional object to see front part of these, we can see the mental state to see the bodily behavior. But this analogy is not so workable because, I can see the whole tomato from the another side or backside but we cannot see the mental state like emotions the way we see the physical object. But we can see at least some part of mental states. For example, dancers or actors can express their emotion through bodily gesture or facial expression. These expression or gesture represent specific mental state. It helps us to communicate to each other. Non-verbal expressive behavior can express the emotion and it helps us in social interaction.

In communication emotion or feeling plays a big role. We have to emotionally aware to communicate with each other. Some researchers explain that, "We do not passively detect information in the world and then react to it -- we construct perceptions of the world as the architects of our own experience. Our affective feelings are a critical determinant of the experience we create, that is, we do not come to know the world through only our external senses -- we see the world differently when we feel pleasant or unpleasant." Emotions are positive or negative energy and the emotional moods are reflect upon our perception or behaviour. Our mental states are about something or it is directed toward something. But all our mental states are not directed towards something. There are something like for me to be is that state and that is qualitative feature of our mental state. In the case of emotion, they affect our perception and behaviour. When we are happy we look the world in a particular way and when someone is under depression , she looks the world in particular way , the world represent to her in particular way. Emotions also play a big role I making a decision. Emotions are very much rational and they are essential for the system of thinking and advise even our most intelligent choices.

II. CONCLUSION

Emotion is some kind of feelings and sometimes is publicly perceivable. By introspection we can know our own mental state but we cannot directly perceive another's mental state. We only can see the outer behavioral expression of any people and emotion is hidden from everyone but some phenomenologist said that to see the expression of emotion is to see the emotion itself. But some philosopher said that the behavioral expressions are not the emotion itself. We often can use emoticons or emoji to show our emotional state in social media. There are many emoji to express our emotion and we all know that which emoji is appropriate of our emotional state. When we chatting with someone and want to show our self happy we can use happy emoji to express our emotion. Sometimes we are angry or sad about any matter and we share our emotion through emojis in social media. In social media or in our virtual life we can understand other persons emotion through emoji.

In our social interaction some forms of bodily behavior constitute proper parts of our emotion. So we can see the emotion in action. We immediately see or directly perceive the emotions or feelings or our intention. When we see the expressive behavior or bodily movement of other persons we see the meaning of these. When we see smiling face or frown of another people we can see the associated mental phenomena like anger or happiness. So when we see the human being we can see both physical and mental properties. Non reductionists said that mental properties are not reducible to physical properties. We can directly see the bodily behavior but we can't see the mentality or emotion directly. Others mental state is not perceptual, is inferential. We see the bodily behavior but we don't see the mental phenomena in and of themselves. Angry behavior is different from the property of anger itself. So we cannot directly know the mentality through perception. But in our social life when we see the angry gesture of someone we can see the anger also. We can say that perception give us direct access to part of another's mental state without inferencing and simulating. Genuine expression of any mental state like anger is spontaneous in nature. So direct perception helps us to know the mental states. In this view inference is secondary way to know others mental states. We don't have to infer some mental states because we can directly see this. So we see the emotions of other people. I immediately feel the happiness when I am happy and when another people are happy ,I don't feel the happiness, I can see it because I cannot perceive the happiness of others people from first person point of view.

Sometimes we might be deceived in our perception of happiness by illusion or hallucination but this is not just cases where we directly perceive another's mentality. We perceive another's happiness directly. There is no difference between direct feeling of my emotion and the emotion of other people. We saw that emotion has both private and public entities. And our decision making system is very much influenced by emotion.

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IV. REFERENCES

- [1] **Guttenplan, Samuel.** A Companion to the Philosophy of Mind. Oxford: Blackwell, 1994.
- [2] **Kim, Jaegwon.** Philosophy of Mind. Boulder (Colo.): Westview Press, 2011.
- [3] **Krueger, Joel.** "Emotions and Other Minds." Rethinking Emotion, n.d. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110259254.324>.
- [4] **Krueger, Joel.** "Seeing Mind in Action." Phenomenology and the Cognitive Sciences 11, no. 2 (2011): 149-73. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11097-011-9226-y>.
- [5] **León, Felipe, Thomas Szanto, and Dan Zahavi.** "Emotional Sharing and the Extended Mind." Synthese 196, no. 12 (2017): 4847-67. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-017-1351-x>.
- [6] **Melnyk, Andrew.** "Inference to the Best Explanation and Other Minds." Australasian Journal of Philosophy 72, no. 4 (1994): 482-91. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00048409412346281>.
- [7] **www.emerald.com**
- [8] **www.en.m.wikipedia.org**
- [9] **www.intechopen.com**
- [10] **www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov**
- [11] **www.psychreg.org**
- [12] **www.sciencedaily.com**
- [13] **www.zendesk.com**
